

ARDUINO BASED ICU PATIENT HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEM OVER IOT

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ABSTRACT

This article introduces a system of wearable health sensors for use in IoT-connected health and safety applications. An Internet of Things (IoT) network system that can monitor all health indicators and update wirelessly is crucial for the safety and well-being of intensive care unit (ICU) patients in hospitals. Wearable sensors track physiological and environmental variables in the suggested network architecture. Through an Internet of Things (IoT) platform medical signal detecting network, wearable sensors on various individuals may exchange data with one another and send it to a gateway. The suggested system incorporates a parallel processing CPU with sensors that measure heart rate, temperature, alcohol, and air quality. Sensors collect data on vital signs and transmit it to the ARDUINO board. This module processes the data, displays it on the LCD, and then uploads it to a server that is based on the internet of things. We keep a close eye on the patient at all times, and the IoT system notifies the appropriate parties if it detects any changes, such as an abnormally low or high heart rate, temperature, or movement. Data processing, a local web server, and a link to the cloud are all made possible by an intelligent IoT gateway. The information gathered by the wearable sensors is sent to an Internet of Things (IoT) cloud via the gateway, which then stores, processes, and displays the data.

1. INTRODUCTION

Experts in the healthcare industry are capitalising on the new opportunities presented by these advancements, which may lead to significant improvements in areas outside of medicine. In a similar vein, many everyday users make use of the features offered by Health and Electronic Health applications (therapeutic organisations administered by ICT) to build, maintain, and improve their healthcare network. In an emergency, the patient may send an SMS to a doctor or a trusted family member. A major shift is taking place as health experts gradually grasp the benefits these innovations bring to the healthcare social security industry. Similarly, countless regular consumers are assisting their health professionals via the use of M-Health (Mobile Health) applications and Health. A major shift is taking place as health experts gradually grasp the benefits these innovations bring to the healthcare social security industry. M-Health (Mobile Health) apps and Health are also assisting countless regular consumers in assisting their health professionals. Part of this related method that is reliable and persistent quickly. A appearance similar to structure (PMS). The absence of social security is a major problem for our society. Legislative bodies of the World Health Organisation (WHO) show that people benefit much from the medical system's top characteristic. You need a flash like the new mending machine if you want to convince and make people look. In a sustainable and cautious way, the social

insurance system will include deeper remedial ties for individuals everywhere. Assuming that these devices enable them to assist the environment while also ensuring the steady, well-structured growth of social security and organisations in the digital realm. The core principle of the Internet of Things (IoT) rests on sensors, components, and remote systems that enable users to authorise and access applications and data. But in the regions treated for prosperity, the IOT across all zones was most noticeable. "Prosperity is money" is a cliché, yet getting better outcomes is very crucial. Hence, establishing a connection to an IoT framework that offers safe and fruitful analysis is crucial. Right now, the contraction of human institutions, the conventional way of coping with a technologically advanced personally driven oriented system, is being traded. As the age profile of many societies continues to increase, in addition to the increasing population of people affected by chronic diseases, including diabetes, cardiovascular disease, obesity, and so on, supporting health, both mentally and physically, is of increasing crucial for the preservation of self-sufficiency. The use of sensing technology, together with remote health monitoring and, eventually, the ability to identify ADLs, has shown promise as a solution. From a technological standpoint, the IoT is quickly becoming a hot topic across many fields, particularly in individualised healthcare. At the same time, the Internet of Things (IoT) framework's body area sensor network (BASN) has seen extensive use in fields such as ubiquitous health monitoring. Monitoring electrocardiograms (ECGs) has become an essential tool in the diagnosis of cardiac illness. What follows is a list of the paper's primary contributions: To begin, this article introduces a new method for tracking personal health in real-time: the WISE (Wearable IoT-cloud-based health monitoring system). To provide continuous health monitoring, WISE uses the BASN (body area sensor network) architecture. Heart rate, core temperature, and blood pressure sensors are

just a few of the integrated wearables. Second, most current wearable health monitoring solutions are dependent on smartphones for data processing, visualisation, and transmission, which may disrupt regular smartphone use. While in WISE, data is sent immediately to the cloud via the BASN, and an alternate approach for seeing the data quickly in real-time is to install a lightweight wearable LCD. Worldwide population growth and demographic shifts have occurred throughout the previous few decades and are likely to continue into the foreseeable future. The health and healthcare sectors are among the many that stand to lose the most from these demographic shifts. It is cause for celebration that life expectancy has risen substantially, particularly in wealthier countries; this is a chance for people to enjoy better, longer lives. The healthcare system and housing conditions must be significantly upgraded for this to happen, however, since healthcare needs of the elderly tend to outstrip those of younger generations. Another aspect of becoming older is an increased risk of developing chronic diseases. At the same time that this demographic time bomb is going off, healthcare costs are skyrocketing in every country.

The global population is growing at an alarming rate. additional people living in cities means additional strain on already-crowded metropolitan areas. The sufficiency level is still not reached, despite the constant expansion of medical resources and facilities in cities. The increasing need for effective healthcare management in urban areas has spurred technological innovation to address these growing issues. Remote healthcare has become an integral part of our lives due to the rise in the number of individuals who are medically challenged. We have seen a rise in the popularity of wearable sensors in recent years, and these gadgets are now accessible for a lower price for use in monitoring one's health and activities. Medical applications for data

recording, management, and continuous monitoring were investigated for deployment of such sophisticated devices by researchers. health of the patient. One emerging technology that might take health care to the next level is the Internet of Things [1]. In order to facilitate smooth networking among patients, medical equipment, and doctors, it guarantees that inexpensive, dependable, and conveniently placed gadgets may be carried or integrated with patients. In order to convey vital physiological characteristics, the sensors will continuously capture signals, which are then correlated, and relayed over the wireless network. The data that is generated is then integrated with the current health records for storage, processing, and analysis [2]. With the use of accessible data records and decision support tools, the doctor may make a more accurate prediction and recommend therapy sooner rather than later. Thanks to this study, modern technology can anticipate health problems even when a doctor isn't accessible. Machines can do more than just make predictions; they can also systematically research pharmaceutical databases and produce drugs. Technological advancements will drastically improve the precision of illness forecasts and have a profound effect on the way people live their lives and keep tabs on their health. We outline the current obstacles to deploying the Internet of Things (IoT) in the actual medical sector, as well as a service model that would put patients at ease from a technical and economic perspective, in this article.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

3. [1] We have looked at the many tests that have been conducted using current methods that have been used in patient health screening. Recent developments in persistent checking frameworks and associated work on the remote patient observation framework are reviewed in this article.

It is suggested to use a structure for an IoT-based health checking system. Distributed computing and the Internet of Things (IoT) are showcased in this article. A patient's vitals, including their heart rate, oxygen saturation, and blood temperature, are monitored by the suggested model. Data tenacity is enhanced via distributed computing. To make it accessible from anywhere in the world, the data collected by the sensors worn by patients is stored on the cloud. With the specialist's login, the patient's information may be accessed and a health report can be generated. After logging onto the portal, patients will have access to the wellness report. In order to facilitate communication between specialists and patients, the website provides a visit option. The framework eliminates the barrier of separation by functioning as an extension of the doctor-patient relationship. It is an economical and practical solution for rural areas without access to adequate medical facilities. [3] Considering the needs of the elderly, a health monitoring system based on Arduino is suggested. The need for a specialised health monitoring system is growing in a society where populations are living longer. Here, the suggested framework monitors core body temperature, blood pressure, and pulse rate before relaying the data to medical professionals. The characteristics of these borders are important indicators of a patient's health status, hence they are often assessed during basic health checkups. An alarm button is set up so that the expert will get an SMS message whenever the button is pushed in case of an emergency. The web worker receives data so that both the specialist and the patient may see the attributes. The primary test that was seen was how long it took for the older generation to adopt this new technology. They need to learn how to use modern mechanical devices, such as computers and

mobile phones. [4]The integration of Android with wireless Bluetooth technology is being studied for remote health monitoring and fall detection. Various health parameters are monitored by the system, including electrocardiogram (ECG), temperature, "body pose," "fall recognition," and current GPS location. In order to transfer the data, many synchronous Bluetooth relationships are established with an Android phone. The data is also processed and provided to the employee over the internet using an android app. As soon as a crisis occurs, information is sent to the designated person to handle the situation. People in high-risk situations, such as those protecting high-altitude areas, travellers, unskilled labourers, etc., may benefit from this plan's versatility, energy efficiency, lightweight design, and adaptability. Wireless technology has been more important in meeting the needs of many different industries in recent years. The Internet of Things (IoT) has recently swept the industrial sector, particularly the control and automation subsets. One of the newest fads in health care improvement is biomedical. Healthcare facilities, both public and private, are becoming more accessible thanks to the Internet of Things (IoT). In order to save expenses, maximise efficiency, and control power consumption, a smart system monitors a number of characteristics. The review of this publication is based on this intelligent system. When it comes to conventional medicine, physicians are still very much involved in routine checkups. It takes a long time to complete the registration, appointment, and check-up steps of this procedure. A report is also created at a later stage. Because of how long it takes, working individuals sometimes put off or completely disregard their checks. Time is saved in the process by using this contemporary method. In order to meet the

demands of many different industries, wireless technology has become more popular in recent years. The Internet of Things (IoT) has recently made a beeline for the automation and control sectors of industry. Improved health care has been a recent trend, and biomedical is one of them. Thanks to the Internet of Things (IoT), health care facilities are opening up in all kinds of places, not only hospitals. Having a smart system allows for the observation of several characteristics that impact power consumption, cost, and efficiency. This work is evaluated in line with this intelligent system. [5]For decades, researchers and innovators in the medical industry have worked towards the goal of improving people's health and quality of life. We cannot overlook the significance of their work in the medical field. Ideas from yesterday's fundamentals provide the basis for today's vehicle structures. In addition These technologies make it possible to diagnose chronic illnesses at an early stage. [6]Primary indicators of illness include vital signs such as temperature, pulse, blood pressure, and respiratory rate. In this project, we use the Internet of Things to provide temperature and heart rate readings. Wearable tech and the "cloud of things" are examples of the new technology incorporated into the modern healthcare system. It offers versatility in terms of remotely sending patient monitored data via IoT and recording it. Secure data transfer is necessary for this connection. The primary goal of this study is to ensure the secure transmission of data. The suggested method incorporates healthcare security and the internet of things. The system's two primary phases are data storage and retrieval. The data is saved and updated for later use at the storage step. Retrieve data from the cloud during the data retrieval step. Authenticated users may request to share files from the cloud

server. A patient's record is continuously updated every 5 or 10 minutes by use of wearable gadgets. It refreshes every minute when in emergency mode. Using a Bluetooth connection or near field communication (NFC), the wearable gadget will transmit the findings to the phone. This may be sent to a server in the cloud over GSM and 3G networks. Every patient is assigned a unique address at the cloud server. Thus, the data stored in the cloud can verify the patient's identity and fulfil the necessary request. [7] To meet the demands of home-based mobile health and personalised medicine, telemonitoring systems are developing via WBAN. In order to record the output, WBAN may gather data from sensors. The findings of this output are sent wirelessly to the health monitoring system's controller. This document makes use of Zigbee

because health telemonitoring systems rely on WBAN technology, which guarantees a delay. Zigbee is used for the correspondence.

[8] In their explanation of low power WAN networks for performing analysis of monitored data in healthcare systems, Afef Mdhaffar, Tarak Chaari, Kaouthar Larbi, Mohamed Jmaiel, and Bernd Freisleben highlight their work. With a range of 33m² and an altitude of around 12 m, they have set up a WAN network for communication. In addition, they proved that the Lora WAN network uses ten times less power than the GPRS/3G/4G networks. You may learn about the Internet of Things (IoT) in a methodical way with the help of the provided architecture. Lora WAN is primarily designed to reduce energy usage. In idle mode, Lora WAN consumes 2.8mA of power, while GPRS uses 20mA. In contrast to GPRS, which costs fifty dollars for hardware, Lora WAN is just ten dollars. In contrast to GPRS, which allows for data rates of up to 86.5 kbps uplink and 14 kbps

downlink, Lora WAN limits data rates to 50 kbps uplink and 50 kbps downstream. Lora WAN's overall efficiency in demonstrating an IoT for health monitoring system is shown by these findings.

[9] In a variety of contexts and at varied intervals, Mohammed Adel Serhani, Alramzana Nujum Navaz, and Mohammad M. Masud measured electrocardiogram signals. Concerns of energy consumption, computer resource constraints, and loss of network continuity have all been explored. A mathematical model has been created to tackle these difficulties in a sequential fashion. The procedure may be worked out using one of three methods. The first two methods are data mining and machine learning, while the third is a mobile-based monitoring strategy. Sunil Kumar, Anurag Bajpai, and Ayush Bansal The creation of a system that can identify catastrophic cardiac events is the primary emphasis of Vijay N. Tiwari, Mithun Nayak, Shankar Venkatesan, and Rangavittal Narayanan. In order to prevent deadly cardiac episodes, a state-of-the-art remote monitoring technology is being used to identify warning signs. the eleventh As design parameters for decision making, Hamid Al-Hamadi and Ing-Ray Chen provide a trust-based health IoT protocol that takes risk categorization, reliability trust, and loss of health probability into account. Evaluating the practicability via a comparison of trust-based protocols with baseline procedures.

[12] Thangaraj Muthuraman [name] Punitha Ponmalar and Pichaiah S Anuradha Subramanian. The phrase "digital hospital" is used to describe the way hospitals are run. Automatic electronic medical records in standard form are made possible by it. Moreover, it delves into the practical use of IoT in smart autonomous hospital administration.

4. EXISTING SYSTEM

In existing system of health monitoring system many sensors are used to measure the health parameters temperature, body motion, pulse rate all are measure and displays in LCD only. In existing model we don't have data transfer through longer distance using any wireless communication. To secure the patient health the proposed model implemented with IOT setup automatically sends alerts to doctor and relative in case of emergency.

5. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In the proposed system of health monitoring system we used temperature sensor, heart beat sensor and humidity sensor for monitoring the human body health parameters and display in LCD and IOT server. If the heart rate fluctuations mean if we got low BP or HIGH BP then buzzer module automatically alerts and same thing will update in server.

Fig.1. Block diagram

The goal of this approach is to construct a well-organized system for remote monitoring of health. The challenge that the NRF

innovation expert will confront is keeping tabs on the patient's vital signs, like their temperature and heart rate. The evaluation of patients' well-being is in line with the care services provided by medical centres. In order to keep track of the patient's vitals, we constantly take their temperature and pulse. An easy-to-understand interface that showcases the IoT Patient Safety Monitoring Program's use of the ESP8266 and Arduino platforms. Pulse and LM35 temperature sensors track heart rate and outside temperature independently. The programme is created by the Arduino and shown on a 16*2 LCD screen. Connects the ESP8266 device to both WiFi networks and begins transmitting data to the Internet of Things application server. The Internet of Things (IoT) server is the talking part here. Lastly, the only way to verify data from any location is to discover the channel that the Thing speaks. What follows is an explanation of the hardware components that would make up this proposed system.

Advantages

1. Auto alerting system
2. wireless data access through IOT
3. Efficient and low cost design.
4. Low power consumption.
5. Applications
6. Hospitals Home

7. RESULT

We used Arduino for the hardware design of the electronic health monitoring system. Sensors for temperature, humidity, vibration, and heart rate are included into the input modules. An LCD and the internet of things will show the data generated from all the sensors. With the help of the thing-speak database, the buzzer module in this case can send out notifications when the temperature, heart rate, or both are too high or too low.

8. Arduino is integrated with all sensors, including a heart rate monitor, temperature sensor, and humidity sensor. Figure 11 shows the first display of all sensor data on the LCD panel. Figure 11 illustrates that in example 1, the heart rate is 95 and in case 2, it is 125. A high heart rate is one example of this. This time, when the pulse rate is too high, the buzzer will sound an alarm and notify the Internet of Things. A high-heart-rate alarm is shown on the LCD module that also shows the body temperature. Arduino is integrated with all sensors, including a heart rate monitor, temperature sensor, and humidity sensor. Figure 12 shows the first display of all sensor data on the LCD panel. You can see the heart rate 25 in Figure 12. A high heart rate is one example of this. This time, when the pulse rate is too high, the buzzer will sound an alarm and notify the Internet of Things. An LCD module shows vitals including heart rate and temperature, and also sounds an alarm if the heart rate drops too low. When connected to a server, health metrics including temperature, humidity, and heart rate may be shown in real time over the internet of things. When the patient is in an emergency, it notifies us

via data on high and low heart rates. Figure 13 displays the data that has been uploaded to the IoT server and the data that is being continuously monitored.

9. CONCLUSION

We developed and deployed an IoT health monitor using an Arduino processor, which communicates wirelessly with a system of interconnected devices and devices that measure things like temperature, alcohol concentration, air quality, and heart rate. The monitor also features an LCD display, a buzzer, and the internet of things. The suggested solution used the thing speak platform to track and record a variety of health data. The suggested system monitored and warned based on the values of these parameters. Additional sensors, such as glucometers and devices that measure body fat, will be added to the health monitoring system in the future.

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